

Figure S1. Telomeres in the *asf1a1b* double mutant are shortened without disruption of telomerase activity.

Telomere length of mutant plants determined by terminal restriction fragment analysis in WT, (a) *asf1a1b* (F2 and F3 generation), (b) *asf1a* (G2 and G3 generation) and (c) *asf1b* (G2 and G3 generation). In F2 (or G2) three sister plants (1-3) are shown with corresponding progeny in F3 (or G3). All seeds were obtained from another study (Zhu *et al.*, 2011), initial generations for single mutants *asf1a* and *asf1b*, and *asf1a1b* double mutants are not known. Double mutant *asf1a1b* plants were propagated from the filial generation (Fx) for an additional two generations (F2 and F3).

Figure S2. Telomere length in *fas1* or *fas2* mutants deficient for ASF1A or ASF1B.

Telomere length of mutant plants compared to WT determined by terminal restriction fragment analysis with consequent evaluation of the range of telomere signals by the WALTER software.

(a,b) Pools of 14-day-old seedlings of multiple generations (F3, F4, and F5) of double mutants compared to WT. As controls, *asf1a*, *asf1b* and *asf1a1b* were used. Telomere length is not significantly different in *asf1 fas1* or *asf1 fas2* double from *ASF1 fas1* or *ASF1 fas2* single mutants segregated from the corresponding crosses. T-test showed non-significant telomere shortening in all double mutants and their corresponding controls compared to WT.

Figure S3. *asf1a1b* double mutants show no chromosomal aberrations and globally unaffected nuclear volume and sphericity except for larger nuclear volume in guard cells.

(a) Representative images of an anaphase, anaphase bridge and delayed chromosomes from WT and *asf1a1b* mutant plants, coloured by 4',6-Diamidino-2-phenylindole dihydrochloride (DAPI). *asf1a1b* double mutant plants with the lowest 45S *rDNA* copy number (replicate 2b - two individual plants) were used.

(b) Quantification of chromosomal aberrations in *asf1a1b* mutants obtained by microscopic analysis. No anaphase bridges and 3 delayed chromosomes were observed in 1458 anaphases in the *asf1a1b* mutant, while 5 anaphase bridges and 6 delayed chromosomes were observed in 2088 anaphases from WT plants.

(c) Quantification of nuclear volume and nuclear sphericity in guard cell (GC) and pavement cell (PC) nuclei from the cotyledon epidermis of three independent biological replicates. GC: WT 1, n = 193; WT 2, n = 189; WT 3, n = 154; *asf1a1b* 1, n = 147; *asf1a1b* 2, n = 151; *asf1a1b* 3, n = 122. PC: WT 1, n = 72; WT 2, n = 225; WT 3, n = 134; *asf1a1b* 1, n = 72; *asf1a1b* 2, n = 293; *asf1a1b* 3, n = 147. **** p < 0.005 Tukeys multiple comparison test.

Figure S4. Control experiments for protein-protein interaction tests by Bimolecular Fluorescence Complementation.

Bimolecular Fluorescence Complementation (BiFC) on protoplasts from root tips of 10-day-old seedlings. Protoplasts were co-transfected with empty vector nYFP with cYFP/ASF1A, cYFP/ASF1B, cYFP/HIRA, cYFP/TRB1, cYFP/H3.1 and cYFP/H3.3, or with nYFP/RID, nYFP/ASF1A, nYFP/ASF1B and nYFP/HIRA with empty vector cYFP.

Bright field, nuclear localization signal mRFP-NLS (magenta, used as a transformation control), the YFP fluorescence (yellow) and the combined images were visualized under a confocal microscope 16 h after transfection. The scale bar represents 10 μm . Experiments were repeated twice with similar results.

Figure S5. ASF1 proteins interact with NRP histone chaperones.

(a) Bimolecular Fluorescence Complementation (BiFC) in protoplasts from root tips of 10-day-old seedlings. Protoplasts were co-transfected with nYFP/ASF1A and nYFP/ASF1B with cYFP/NRP1 and cYFP/NRP2. Bright field, nuclear localization signal mRFP-NLS (magenta, used as a transformation control), the YFP fluorescence (yellow) and the combined images were visualized under a confocal microscope 16 h after transfection. The scale bar represents 10 μ m. Experiments were repeated twice with similar results.

(b) Graphical representation of the obtained results of interactions of NRP1 and NRP2 with ASF1A and ASF1B proteins. Number of protoplasts used in the graphs: NRP1 + ASF1A: 5, NRP1 + ASF1B: 9, NRP2 + ASF1A: 8, NRP2 + ASF1B: 22.

(c) Co-immunoprecipitation analysis (CoIP) of FAS2 with ASF1A and ASF1B. As a sample (S) radioactively labeled FAS2 with non-radioactively labeled Myc-tagged ASF1A or ASF1B were used. In negative control (NC) Myc-tagged interaction partner was omitted. Unbound (U) and bound (B, protein-protein interaction) fractions were analyzed.

Figure S6. Telomere length in *hira* single mutants.

Telomere length of *hira* mutant plants compared to WT determined by terminal restriction fragment analysis. 14-day-old seedlings of two independent generations G5 (1) and G7 (2) of *hira* single mutants. T-test showed non-significant telomere shortening in both generations compared to WT.

Figure S7. Nuclear volume and shape are unchanged in GC and PC epidermis nuclei in *hira* mutants compared to WT.

Nuclear volume and nuclear sphericity, determined for *hira* mutants in guard cell (GC) and pavement cell (PC) nuclei of the cotyledon epidermis of three independent biological replicates. Note that the WT nuclei are the same as in Figure 2E&F, Figure S2 and Figure 4F and that, in each biological replicate, WT, *hira* and *asf1a1b* mutant plants were processed together. GC: WT 1, n = 193; WT 2, n = 189; WT 3, n = 154; *hira* 1, n = 115; *hira* 2, n = 194; *hira* 3, n = 64. PC: WT 1, n = 72; WT 2, n = 225; WT 3, n = 134; *hira* 1, n = 67; *hira* 2, n = 160; *hira* 3, n = 59. No significant differences in volume or sphericity in GCs and PCs between WT and *hira* were observed (Tukey's multiple comparison test).

Figure S8. H3 occupancy at telomeres in *asf1a1b* plants compared to WT.

(a) Abundance of telomeric repeats and (b) relative H3 occupancy at telomeres are shown as RPM (reads containing telomere sequences per million reads mapped to the genome) in WT and *asf1a1b* mutants in two available ChIP-seq data sets (Zhong *et al.*, 2022). Anova one-way and Dunnett's test revealed no significant differences between WT and *asf1a1b*.

Figure S9. ASF1 and HIRA proteins do not interact with TEN, but ASF1 is present at telomeres.

Bimolecular Fluorescence Complementation (BiFC) using protoplasts from root tips of 10-day-old seedlings. Images show root protoplasts co-transfected with (a) nYFP/ASF1A, nYFP/ASF1B or nYFP/HIRA with cYFP/TEN.

Bright field, nuclear localization signal mRFP-NLS (magenta, used as a transformation control), the YFP fluorescence (yellow) and the combined images were visualized under a confocal microscope 16 h after transfection. The scale bar represents 10 μ m. Experiments were repeated twice with similar results.

(b) ASF1-FLAG ChIP-seq in WT, data from Zhong *et al.* (2022) were checked for quality and mapped. Due to the lacking annotation, reads were mapped to telomeric sequences and plotted as RPM (Reads per million). R1 and R2 represent two independent replicas.

Figure S10. Evaluation of the telomere/45S rDNA signals in WT and *asf1a1b* mutant nuclei obtained by super-resolution microscopy (2D SIM) using Imaris software.

(a) Raw 2D SIM image of the nuclei of 10-day-old *A. thaliana* WT seedlings (left) and object detection in Imaris (right). For signal (green arrows), a mask (green/grey - boxes) was implemented. These signals were automatically discriminated by the object detection algorithm and manually checked for possible artefacts (in the case of telomeres, the focus was on foci accumulating near the nucleolus, confirmed by the 45S rDNA signal). Then the volume/area was measured, respectively.

(b) Representative images of WT and *asf1a1b* mutant nuclei. Clusters of 2-3 signals occur in most nuclei from both WT and *asf1a1b*. Most of the nuclei are elongated. On average, 7.66 and 7.26 telomeric spots per nucleus (WT and *asf1a1b*, respectively) and 2.61 and 2.52 45S rDNA spots per nucleus (WT and *asf1a1b*, respectively) were counted, suggesting that the analysed cell populations were similar in terms of ploidy. 30 nuclei of WT and *asf1a1b* were manually analysed for telomeric spots and 23 nuclei of WT and *asf1a1b* were analysed for rDNA.

Table S1. List of interacting proteins identified in an Y2H screen using ASF1A and ASF1B as baits.

Bait (pGBKT7)	Prey (pGADT7)
ASF1A	H3.3 (AT4G40030)
	FASCIATA 2, FAS2 (AT5G64630)
	Emb1220/PRP31 (AT1G60170)
	RNase III-like protein 1, RTL1 (AT1G80650)
	BCCP-like protein 1, BLP1 (AT1G52670)
	HEMC, RUGOSA1, RUG1 (AT5G08280)
	ARM repeat family protein (AT3G02710)
	GTP binding elongation factor Tu family protein, EF1 α (AT5G60390)
	PTAC16 (AT3G46780)
	SIR (AT5G04590)
	DNA glycosylase superfamily protein (AT1G13635)
	Diacylglycerol acyltransferase family, DGAT2 (AT3G51520)
	Calcium-dependent lipid-binding CaLB domain (AT2G33320)
	NUDX27 (AT5G06340)
	Cotton fiber protein, putative DUF761 (AT1G11210)
	Galactose mutarotase-like superfamily protein (AT5G15140)
	Voltage dependent anion channel 3 (AT5G15090)
	DNA topoisomerase I alpha (AT5G55300)
	Nucleoporin autopeptidase (AT1G59660)
	Peptide deformylase 1B, PDF1B (AT5G14660)
PNM1 (AT5G60960)	
CLK4-associating serine/arginine-rich protein (AT4G36980)	
COP9 signalosome 5A, CSN5A, AJH1 (AT1G22920)	
Photosystem II reaction center protein, PSB29, THF1 (AT2G20890)	
ASF1B	HISTONE REGULATOR A, HIRA (AT3G44530)
	FASCIATA 2, FAS2 (AT5G64630)
	PAPA1-like family protein (AT3G06660)
	Transcription elongation factor family protein IWSI, TFIIS (AT1G32130)
	RPL23A (AT2G39460)
	Ribosomal protein L19 family protein, L19 (AT4G17560)
	DNAJ heat-shock containing protein (AT2G05250)
	MAGO NASHI, MAGO (AT1G02140)
	Membrane Occupation and Recognition Nexus repeat-containing protein, MORN, embryo defective 1211, emb1211 (AT5G22640)
	High chlorophyll fluorescence 164, HCF164 (AT4G37200)
	DNAJ heat shock family protein (AT2G22360)
	Proline-rich family protein (AT2G28440)

Table S2. BiFC experiments of histone chaperone proteins, empty vectors and H3 variants.

cYFP	nYFP	Number of transformed protoplasts imaged	Localisation	Background
ASF1A	empty	5	5x nucleus	WT
ASF1B	empty	9	5x nucleus/ 4x negative	
HIRA	empty	9	8x nucleus/ 1x negative	
TRB1	empty	3	1x nucleus/ 2x negative	

H3.1	empty	3	3x negative	
H3.3	empty	6	6x negative	
empty	RID	6	1x nucleus/ 5x negative	
empty	ASF1A	6	6x negative	
empty	ASF1B	5	5x negative	
empty	HIRA	4	4x negative	
HIRA	ASF1A	5x	4x nucleus/1x negative	WT
	ASF1B	7x	5x nucleus/2x negative	
H3.1	HIRA	5x	5x negative	
	ASF1A	9x	3x nucleus/ 3x nucleolus/ 3x negative	WT
	ASF1B	6x	3x nucleus/ 3x negative	
	FAS1	22x	13x nucleus/ 1x nucleolus/ 8x negative	
H3.3	7x	2x nucleus/ 5x negative	WT	
H3.3	ASF1A	8x		3x nucleus/ 1x nucleolus/ 4x negative
	ASF1B	8x		3x nucleus/ 5x negative
	FAS1	17x		3x nucleus/ 14x negative
ASF1A	H3.1	16x	3x nucleus/ 4x nucleus+nucleolus/ 9x negative	WT
	H3.3	10x	3x nucleus/ 2x nucleolus/ 5x negative	
ASF1B	H3.1	13x	2x nucleus/ 2x nucleolus/ 9x negative	WT
	H3.3	12x	1x nucleus/ 2x nucleolus/ 9x negative	
FAS2	ASF1A	21x	1x nucleus/ 20x negative	WT
	ASF1B	9x	5x nucleus/4x negative	
NRP1	ASF1A	5x	5x nucleus	WT
	ASF1B	9x	3x nucleus/1x cytoplasm/ 1x cytoplasm + nucleus/ 4x negative	
NRP2	ASF1A	8x	8x nucleus	WT
	ASF1B	22x	21x nucleus/ 1x negative	
ASF1A	ASF1B	5x	2x nucleus/ 3x nucleolus	WT

Table S3. BiFC experiments of histone chaperones with telomeric proteins.

cYFP	nYFP	Number of transformed protoplasts imaged	localisation	background
TRB1	ASF1A	7x	5x nucleus/1x nucleolus/2x negative	WT
	ASF1B	8x	1x nucleolus/7x negative	
TRB1	ASF1A	12x	8x nucleolus/4x negative	<i>fas1</i>
	ASF1B	7x	7x nucleolus	
TRB1	ASF1A	20x	2x nucleus/13x nucleolus/5x negative	<i>hira</i>
	ASF1B	10x	1x nucleus/5x nucleolus/2x nucleus+nucleolus/2x negative	
ASF1A	RID	5x	5x nucleolus	WT
ASF1B		5x	5x nucleolus	
TEN	ASF1A	7x	1x nucleolus/6x negative	WT
	ASF1B	6x	6x negative	
	HIRA	4x	4x negative	

Table S4. List of primers.

	Name	Sequence 5' - 3'	Purpose of use
1	Fas1-4 F1	TAACATGGAGAAGCAAGGGG	<i>fas1-4</i> : genotyping
2	Fas1-4 R1	GATCCTTTTGCAGAGGACGA	<i>fas1-4</i> : genotyping
3	Fas1-4 LBF	TTAAAAACGTCCGCAATGTG	<i>fas1-4</i> : genotyping
4	Fas2-5 F1	TTTGCCCTGTTGCATTTAAAC	<i>fas2-5</i> : genotyping
5	Fas2-5 R1	GCCCAATAATGATCCACAATG	<i>fas2-5</i> : genotyping
6	Fas2-5 LBF	ATTTTGCCGATTTCCGGAAC	<i>fas2-5</i> : genotyping
7	Asf1a F1	TCACCAACGTCGCTGTATTG	<i>asf1a</i> : genotyping
8	Asf1a R1	GGATCATGATTCTCAGGTTTTGG	<i>asf1a</i> : genotyping
9	Asf1a F2	TCTCTCCCGAGTTTGGATGAAG	<i>asf1a</i> : genotyping
10	GABI LB	TTGGACGTGAATGTAGACAC	<i>asf1a</i> : genotyping
11	Asf1b F1	GAAGCTTTTGTGGCTGCTCAAG	<i>asf1b</i> : genotyping
12	Asf1b R1	TCACACATTACTAGTTGCAAGTTA	<i>asf1b</i> : genotyping
13	LB 405	CAACACTCAACCCTATCTCGG	<i>asf1b</i> : genotyping
14	Hira F1	GAGAGTCACTGTTTTGGCTGG	<i>hira</i> : genotyping
15	Hira R1	CTACTAAAATTTGAGGCCGGG	<i>hira</i> : genotyping
16	Hira LBF	AACGTCCGCAATGTGTTATTAAGTTGTC	<i>hira</i> : genotyping
17	UBQ F	AACGGGAAAGACGATTAC	<i>UBIQUITIN 10</i> : qPCR
18	UBQ R	ACAAGATGAAGGGTGGAC	<i>UBIQUITIN 10</i> : qPCR
19	18S rDNA F	CTAGAGCTAATACGTGCAACAAAC	18S rDNA: qPCR
20	18S rDNA R	GAATCGAACCCCTAATTCTCCG	18S rDNA: qPCR
21	p3-5allrDNAvar	GACAGACTTGTCCAAAACGCCAC	45S rDNA variants: semi-qPCR
22	p4-3allrDNAvar	CTGGTCGAGGAATCCTGGACGATT	45S rDNA variants: semi-qPCR
23	5ACTINproRT	AAGTCATAACCATCGGAGCTG	45S rDNA variants: semi-qPCR
24	3ACTINproRT	ACCAGATAAGACAAGACACAC	45S rDNA variants: semi-qPCR

25	TS21	GACAATCCGTCGAGCAGAGTT	TRAP
26	47F	CGCGGTAGTGATGTGGTTGTGTT	TRAP
27	TelCe3	CGTACACCCTAAAAGACCCTAGAAAACC	TRAP
28	HIRA2: B dom- C_attB1	ACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCTCGATATGGAGATGTCAGAG	Gateway cloning
29	HIRA2: B dom- C_attB2	ACAAGAAAGCTGGGTTCAAGAGCCCGAGTCTCT	Gateway cloning
30	ASF1b_F	AAAAAGCAGGCTACATGAGCTCTATCAATATCAC	Gateway cloning
31	ASF1b_StopR	AGAAAGCTGGGTCTCATGTCTCCTGGAGATTTTG	Gateway cloning
32	NRP1 attB1	AAAAAGCAGGCTACATGGTCGCGGACAAGAGCAA	Gateway cloning
33	NRP1 attB2	AGAAAGCTGGGTCTTACACATCTGTTATAGAAG	Gateway cloning
34	NRP2 attB1	AAAAAGCAGGCTACATGGTGACAGACAAGAGCAAG	Gateway cloning
35	NRP2 attB2	AGAAAGCTGGGTCTCATTCTCACCACCTTCGTCTT	Gateway cloning
36	HTR3 aatB1	GGGGACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTATACCAAT CAAACACGACAGTCT	Gateway cloning
37	HTR3 aatB2	GGGGACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTAAGCCCT CTCACCTCTAATCCTCCT	Gateway cloning
38	HTR5 aatB1	GGGGACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCTCGATGGC TCGTAATAAGCAAACAGCTC	Gateway cloning
39	HTR5 aatB2	GGGGACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGTTAGCACG TTCTCCTCTGATCCTGCG	Gateway cloning
40	attB1	GGGGACAAGTTTGTACAAAAAAGCAGGCT	Gateway cloning
41	attB2	GGGGACCACTTTGTACAAGAAAGCTGGGT	Gateway cloning

Table S5. Primer combinations.

Genotyping	
FAS1-4 WT	1+2
FAS1-4 MUT	2+3
FAS2-5 WT	4+5
FAS2-5 MUT	5+6
ASF1A WT	7+8
ASF1A MUT	9+10
ASF1B WT	11+12
ASF1B MUT	11+13
HIRA WT	14+15
HIRA MUT	14+16
q-PCR	
UBQ	17+18
18S	19+20
45S rDNA variants expression	
rDNA variants	21+22
ACTIN	23+24
TRAP	
TRAP	25(26)+27
Cloning	
HIRA	28+29
ASF1B	30+31
NRP1	32+33
NRP2	34+35
H3.1	36+37
H3.3	38+39
attB1	40
attB2	41

Table S6. Percentage of reads mapping to Drosophila and Arabidopsis genomes in Drosophila-spiked WT, *asf1a1b*, *hira* and *fas1* input and ChIP-seq datasets.

ChIP Input	Percentage of reads mapped to the Drosophila and Arabidopsis genome
Col_input1	96.52
Col_input2	98.69
Col_input3	96.82
Col_input4	98.73
<i>fas1-4</i> _input1	96.51
<i>fas1-4</i> _input2	98.76
<i>fas1-4</i> _input3	96.87
<i>fas1-4</i> _input4	98.88
<i>hira-1</i> _input1	97.45
<i>hira-1</i> _input2	98.87
<i>hira-1</i> _input3	80.56
<i>hira-1</i> _input4	98.44
<i>asf1a1b</i> _input1	97.50
<i>asf1a1b</i> _input2	98.83
<i>asf1a1b</i> _input3	80.15
<i>asf1a1b</i> _input4	98.82

H3 ChIP	Percentage of reads mapped to the Drosophila and Arabidopsis genome
Col_ChIPH3_1	96.45
Col_ChIPH3_2	95.45
<i>fas1-4</i> _ChIPH3_1	96.20
<i>fas1-4</i> _ChIPH3_2	97.37
<i>hira-1</i> _ChIPH3_1	95.78
<i>hira-1</i> _ChIPH3_2	96.84
<i>asf1a1b</i> _ChIPH3_1	96.07
<i>asf1a1b</i> _ChIPH3_2	97.82

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